

The Proof and Trust Shock: Generative AI and the Future of Mass Higher Education (Version 1.2¹)

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Abstract

This paper asks what happens to mass higher education in the United States and United Kingdom when generative AI makes good academic output cheap but makes it harder to prove who did the work. To avoid both utopian and apocalyptic stories, the paper uses scenarios, not forecasts. It sets out six scenarios to 2035 and extends the probability estimates to 2040 as a tail horizon because the biggest effects build over time. The scenarios are organized around four constraints that are already tightening: proof (assessment validity and credential signaling); cost (the price of verified learning at scale); legitimacy (payer and political consent); jobs (entry-level ladders). These constraints are seen metaphorically as four linked “walls” that can move inward forcing change in the prevailing mass model. The most likely development by 2030 is bifurcation, with a small group of relatively well-endowed and well-led institutions having developed reliable ways to assess the learning of their graduates in an AI-dominated world, while most universities have failed to do so. By 2035 the modal outcome shifts toward a legitimacy crisis as proof disputes and cost pressures become politically visible to all. By 2040, there is a significant risk that the current system of mass higher education could collapse. The paper ends with practical indicators for updating the probabilities and argues that institutional reforms matter but cannot replace a wider public agreement on transitions to the workplace, proof of educational attainment, and who pays.

Keywords

Generative AI; higher education; scenario planning; assessment validity; credential signaling; unit economics; legitimacy and governance

1. Introduction

This paper examines how generative AI could reshape BA-level higher education between 2026 and 2035, with longer tail effects extending toward 2040. The focus is on the higher education systems of the United States and the United Kingdom, but the conclusions are likely valid for massified higher education systems in other countries as well, particularly in Australia and Canada.² The core claim is simple. AI presents a challenge to the current higher education status quo because it makes what appears to be high-quality student output easier to produce while making credible proof of student learning harder to demonstrate. This new normal produces a spread of plausible futures, driven by incentives, internal university governance capacity, labor-market responses, and institutional adaptation.

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² By mass higher education, we mean BA-level education delivered primarily in traditional classroom settings at relatively large institutions (more than 2000 students enrolled) and credentialed through grades received by students for completing primarily written work (essays, take-home exams, problem sets, etc.). In the US, a bit over 60% of university students are enrolled at the BA level and of those 75% (≈15M) are enrolled at what we call mass universities). See <https://educationdata.org/college-enrollment-statistics> for details. In Great Britain 72% of higher education students are enrolled at the BA level (≈2M) almost all of whom attend what we call mass institutions (see <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/20-03-2025/sb271-higher-education-student-statistics>). We do not address how the pressures we describe here would affect MA or PhD-level learning, nor do we consider vocational schools, associates degrees, or so-called liberal arts colleges.

Methodologically, the paper uses scenario planning as a disciplined alternative to point forecasting. Scenarios are treated as structured narratives that make assumptions explicit, combine drivers into coherent “worlds,” and allow strategies to be stress-tested against uncertainty (Schoemaker, 1995; Schwartz, 1991; Wack, 1985). We present six scenarios in a common format to support comparison.

To keep the analysis grounded, the scenarios are organized around four metaphorical “walls,” understood as binding constraints that can move inward (tighten) or outward (relax).

Figure 1: The Walls are Closing In

- The proof wall concerns whether credentials remain credible evidence of student learning when AI can generate persuasive academic output at low cost
- The cost wall concerns affordability and the sustainability of delivery and regulatory compliance
- The legitimacy wall concerns public and political acceptance, including whether universities retain moral authority under conditions of perceived hypocrisy, weak integrity enforcement, and rising skepticism
- The jobs wall concerns the existing tacit bargain between universities and students/parents/society that a BA degree will lead to better economic outcomes for graduates

The evidence base is intentionally mixed: empirical findings on technology, productivity, and work (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2020; Brynjolfsson et al., 2025; Noy & Zhang, 2023), combined with classic institutional theory on proof, signaling, and verification (Power, 1997; Spence, 1973), and policy frameworks that clarify operational risk and governance expectations (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023; OECD, 2023). The paper’s purpose is therefore not to “predict the winner,” but to clarify what must be true for each future to materialize and indicate what universities can do now to put themselves in a better position to retain their relevance to society.

2. What is mass higher education and why is it vulnerable to changes brought about by AI?

Higher education (also called post-secondary or tertiary education) is a diverse system. We will not treat all aspects of the system here, but rather focus on BA-level education, which has grown exponentially over some 80 years, beginning in the US after World War II and now having penetrated much of the world.

To understand why AI could pose an existential threat to mass universities, we need to appreciate how and on what basis such institutions work. It may seem intuitive that the goal of the higher education system is to provide education, producing young graduates who can absorb and analyze difficult material, think creatively and independently, recognize important problems, develop ways to solve them, and communicate their ideas to others. In fact, while the mass higher education system

sometimes produces these outcomes, education in this sense of the word is not its primary purpose, at least not at the BA level.³ Rather, BA education at mass universities exists to produce competent graduates who can staff an ever-growing knowledge economy which does not demand educated workers but rather trainable employees who possess useful skills. The enormous growth of BA-level programs since WWII can only be understood as a part of an ever-growing virtuous circle, based on a consensus among students, universities, payers (individual families or society), and business. The consensus goes something like this: universities agree to provide skills training which allows BA graduates access to jobs in the growing knowledge economy. In return, universities use the resources provided by these BA students to expand, and faculty recognize that the presence of large numbers of undemanding students who pay the bills gives them the opportunity to pursue their scholarly interests. Parents or society (in those countries where undergraduate education is subsidized by taxes) agree to pay to maximize graduates' individual earning potential and grow the base of solid, tax-paying citizens. Businesses agree to hire graduates, recognizing that the credentials provided by universities, while not ideal measures of qualification, are nevertheless somewhat trustworthy indicators that a graduate knows and can do some things business needs done and is trainable to accomplish future tasks.

If most students were enrolled in BA programs for the purposes of education as defined above, AI would not pose any threat to universities. It would be clear to all that AI, used indiscriminately, interferes with core goals of education, and students and faculty would devise ways to incorporate AI when it could improve educational outcomes and avoid using it when it could not. AI becomes a problem because most students are not enrolled at the BA-level for the purposes of education, but rather to acquire skills and a necessary credential to enter the knowledge economy job market. Under these circumstances, students are incentivized to use the tools available to minimize their required input and universities are happy to give them a credential if they have completed a reasonable amount of work, picked up some useful skills, and are hireable. AI use threatens to undermine this balance, potentially destroying the delicate consensus that has allowed mass BA-level education to grow.

2.1 What does "AI in education" mean?

In this paper, "AI in education" is defined primarily as generative systems that produce or transform the outputs that universities have historically treated as evidence of learning, including text (essays, reports, reflections), code, images, slide decks, feedback comments, lesson materials, and other scholarly communication. This is our focus because the rapid adoption (by students) of such systems directly challenges one of the university's core functions: to act as a credible verifier of capability. When seemingly high-quality output can be produced cheaply and quickly, the traditional equation that student output equals student learning weakens, and the credential's informational, and therefore economic, value becomes harder to defend (OECD, 2026; UNESCO, 2023).⁴

For the scenarios presented here, the key implication is operational. AI in education should be understood predominantly as a set of delegations of cognitive work to generative systems, with a secondary option to commitment to using AI to enhance learning through substantive reform. Under plausible real-world

³ To be sure, in the pre-AI era assignments often required a modicum of thinking, analysis and communication, thereby ensuring that education was smuggled in through the back door as it were and making grades a reasonable, albeit imperfect proxy for measuring skills training levels and educational attainment. Students acceded to this because there was no other way to get the necessary credential and as a result, they received some education as we define it whether they wanted it or not. By producing simulacra of thoughtful work, AI allows students to get the grade without the work, a tempting offer for many. Even if some students continue to do the work themselves, they end up at a disadvantage (grade-wise) vis-à-vis students who rely on AI, because at the BA level AI can produce better work than most students and current assessment regimes do not easily allow universities to differentiate between work done by students themselves or through AI.

⁴ Other applications sit under the same "AI in education" umbrella but are secondary. They include learning analytics and predictive models (early-alert and retention systems), and decision-support automation in admissions, advising, and student services. They matter, but do not strike as directly at the epistemic and evidentiary core of higher education. They can optimize allocation and workflow around an existing model, but do not destabilize what counts as assessable work and, therefore, what counts as proof (Williamson & Eynon, 2020; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023).

conditions, **we argue that AI in education is likely to weaken assessment validity and credential trust more quickly than it can generate system-wide learning gains.** The positive case becomes plausible at scale only if institutions are ready to redesign assessment and verification in ways that are credible, scalable, financially viable, and enforceable.

The most likely near-term equilibrium at most institutions is AI-enabled output substitution outpacing assessment redesign, because generative tools are low-friction, socially normalized, and immediately useful for students, while assessment redesign is slow and messy with no one-size-fits-all solution. The result is a measurement validity problem, not merely a misconduct problem. If grades and credentials rely heavily on take-home text and project documentation, then AI tools expand the set of students who can submit high-quality work without commensurate understanding. The signal sent by the institution (e.g., grades) will become less meaningful (Spence, 1973). In response, universities will likely expand verification and audit routines. These are costly, unevenly applied, and politically contested (Power, 1997), but still easier and cheaper to institute than wholesale changes to the system of assessment and evaluation.

It is possible that AI could have a positive effect on BA mass education, but this is a lower probability over the next 10-15 years precisely because it is institutionally demanding. Generative systems can support learning when used as scaffolds (Vygotsky, 1978) rather than substitutes, providing formative feedback, alternative explanations, language support, practice generation, and structured tutoring. Research indicates that well-designed tutoring systems can improve learning outcomes (Kulik & Fletcher, 2016; Van Lehn, 2011). However, the learning-enhancing pathway requires deliberate design choices that preserve cognitive effort, plus governance choices about disclosure, data protection, evaluation, and accountability (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023; UNESCO, 2023). Those are higher fixed-cost moves than simply allowing chat-based assistance.

3. The four walls: what they are and why they matter

The scenarios that follow explore various possible ways in which AI may weaken the existing consensus that has allowed for the exponential growth of mass higher education and various ways universities might plausibly respond. They are not presented as alternative strategic choices that universities freely select but as outcomes produced by tightening constraints. This framing builds directly on the paper's definition of "AI in education" as the diffusion of generative systems that can produce or transform the outputs universities have traditionally used as proxies for proof of learning. As the marginal cost of producing plausible academic output falls, the sector's core challenge is no longer content scarcity but proof scarcity. **The university's political economy is therefore shaped less by whether it adopts new tools and more by whether it can sustain credible verification, affordable delivery, and social consent under new conditions** (OECD, 2026; UNESCO, 2023; Kasneci et al., 2023).

We capture these pressures metaphorically as four "walls" that can move inward and trap the prevailing mass model. Each wall represents a binding constraint. The walls interact, and that interaction matters. Pushing one wall outward often causes another to tighten. For example, strengthening verification can restore trust, but tends to raise unit costs. Protecting affordability by minimizing verification can stabilize budgets in the short term, but risks erosion of credential credibility.

3.1 The proof wall (the signal wall)

This wall concerns whether credentials still function as credible signals of capability. It is the wall most directly disrupted by generative AI. If students can generate seemingly high-quality outputs without equivalent understanding, familiar assessment formats become weaker measures of competence. The degree becomes a less useful indicator in a market already characterized by information asymmetry (Spence, 1973). The proof wall is also where the risk of "false mastery" arises, since improved outputs can mask weaker underlying learning (OECD, 2026). As employers recognize that proof wall has closed in, they will increasingly demand direct evidence of student mastery. Universities, if they wish to retain their

position as gatekeepers to jobs in the knowledge economy, will need to build verification regimes that make capability transparent.

3.2 The cost wall (the unit economics wall)

The cost wall captures the financial reality of delivering verified learning at scale. Generative AI can reduce some costs, such as drafting or support work, but the measures that genuinely restore proof tend to be labor intensive, including supervision, moderation, oral defenses, and rigorous feedback on iterative work. When institutions increase verification, they often expand “audit-like” infrastructure, with staffing and compliance costs (Power, 1997). If the cost wall tightens, the system faces a set of unattractive responses: raising prices, reducing contact and quality, reducing scope, or shrinking through closures and mergers.

3.3 The legitimacy wall (the consent wall)

The legitimacy wall concerns whether payers and regulators continue to consent to the current model given rising costs, contested outcomes, and visible integrity risks. This wall closes in if stakeholders believe they can no longer trust university credentials as proxies for identifying the employees they need. In an AI saturated environment, legitimacy also depends on institutional governance capacity, including transparency about AI use, risk controls, and accountability for harms, which aligns with emerging risk management expectations (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023). When legitimacy is questioned, systems tend to move from debate to intervention through funding conditions, external audits, and enforced external standards.

3.4 The jobs wall (the ladder wall)

Mass participation rests on a tacit labor market bargain: students accept the cost of time, tuition, and effort because entry level roles are available and degrees continue to influence access and wages. This wall is sensitive to AI because productivity gains, task redesign, and substitution pressures may reduce the number of junior roles in the knowledge economy. Evidence on automation and task reallocation suggests that technological shocks can reconfigure demand for skills and change the structure of opportunity, often unevenly across occupations and regions (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2019). Early evidence on generative AI indicates that output can be produced faster for certain tasks, encouraging organizations to experiment with smaller teams and altered workflows (Brynjolfsson et al., 2023; Noy & Zhang, 2023). If the jobs wall were to close in significantly, universities would not be able to sustain mass demand through pedagogical reform alone.

4. Scenarios for higher education in 2026, 2030 and 2035

4.1 Introduction

The six scenarios presented in this section are designed to discipline judgment about how generative AI may reshape higher education between 2026 and 2040. They are not presented as forecasts, nor are they framed as choices universities can make through leadership preference. Instead, each scenario represents a coherent configuration of incentives and constraints, anchored in the paper’s definition of “AI in education” as primarily the spread of generative systems that can produce or transform the outputs universities have traditionally treated as evidence of learning. Under these conditions, the central scarcity is not content but credible proof, and the core institutional challenge is to maintain verification, affordability, and legitimacy while labor market signals shift (Spence, 1973; Power, 1997).

The scenarios are structured around the four walls introduced in the preceding section. Each wall represents a binding constraint that can tighten faster than universities can adapt. The scenarios differ in which wall tightens first, how strongly the walls interact, and whether institutional responses push any wall outward without causing another to move inward. They therefore translate abstract claims about AI into

observable system dynamics, identifying potential shifts in enrollment behavior, employer screening, regulatory intervention, and institutional differentiation.

Positive

- **Scenario 1. Utopia.** Abundance, a high-income floor, with education as a cultural good. AI drives broad productivity gains and living standards rise for all. A credible income floor reduces economic fear, and the link between BA degrees and jobs weakens. Universities become cultural and civic institutions rather than sorting machines. Costs are managed through productivity and stable funding. Proof is less contested because high stakes credential competition eases. Legitimacy improves as universities are seen as public goods rather than gatekeepers. The system shrinks significantly, however, as it is desired only by those who want education for its own sake.
- **Scenario 2. Building the Common Good.** AI is adopted quickly by society and universities respond quickly, using AI to improve teaching, student support, and operations while protecting academic standards without cost blowout. Proof systems become more rigorous through better assessment design, moderation, and supervised work. Over time the system shrinks as it becomes less closely tied to a weakening jobs wall, but overall legitimacy holds because stakeholders see visible competence, fairness, and value.

Mixed

- **Scenario 3. Muddling along.** AI slows (or diffusion slows) giving universities time to adapt to the new normal. The jobs wall stays mostly intact because the labor market evolves only gradually. Costs bite, but there is time to restructure delivery and staffing. Proof pressures grow but remain manageable with incremental reforms. Legitimacy is strained but not broken. The core story is delayed disruption and a longer runway for institutional adjustment. Assuming the jobs wall does not collapse, the system could remain the same size and even grow.
- **Scenario 4. Bifurcation. The Proof Economy.** Teaching content is abundant and cheap, but validated competence is not. Top-tier universities become verification and licensing institutions at the BA level, retaining legitimacy by reorganizing around defensible assessment, supervision, and verification, investing in high-friction assessments, moderation, supervised work, and auditable portfolios. The jobs wall shifts from "having a degree" to "having proof." Costs at these institutions rise, but the value proposition becomes clearer and more enforceable. Some institutions that cannot meet proof standards retain political and social value for their socialization function even as their credential signal weakens, while others switch to shorter programs, or face merger, teach-out, and reclassification where proof is delivered externally. The system shrinks substantially at the BA level.

Negative

- **Scenario 5. Legitimacy Crisis.** AI is adopted quickly and institutions try to modernize but find it difficult and expensive to change entrenched delivery models. Rampant student AI use lowers perceived value while costs rise and staffing models resist change. Proof deteriorates because assessment is redesigned badly or integrity collapses under weak enforcement. Students and parents continue to buy degrees but increasingly treat them as defensive consumption. Legitimacy erodes slowly through accumulating disappointment rather than scandal. Eventually, society turns on universities, which lose public trust, not only because of cost, but also because of perceived hypocrisy, weak proof, and low relevance. Governments tighten rules and funding, employers discount degrees, and media scrutiny accelerates cynicism. Proof expectations rise while institutional autonomy shrinks. Institutions become reactive, compliance-driven, and vulnerable to scandal. Unbundling accelerates as external actors build parallel pathways perceived as more transparent and job linked. The sector survives, but with reduced authority and increased external control.

- **Scenario 6. Apocalypse.** AI shocks the entry-level labor market faster than social policy can respond. Degree demand becomes unstable because the jobs wall fails. Families pull back as returns look uncertain and debt aversion rises. Institutions face rapid revenue contraction, layoffs, and closures. Proof disputes become secondary to survival. Legitimacy breaks as universities are seen as expensive insurance that no longer pays out. Enrollment crashes.

Each scenario is written using a consistent template. It begins with key characteristics, then outlines higher education impacts and stakeholder logic for 2026, 2030, and 2035. It closes with a bottom line and a short set of indicators that would make early movement toward the scenario visible.

4.2 Scenario 1: Utopia: Abundance, high income floor, education as a cultural good

4.2.1 Key characteristics

In 2026, generative AI is already powerful and widely accessible but continues to operate inside a familiar work-and-wages template. Household security remains uneven, and political debate is still dominated by conflicts around employability, costs, and distribution. AI productivity gains are real, but they do not yet translate into a stable social contract that decouples livelihoods from paid work. By 2030, a credible income floor is adopted at scale, whether as Universal Basic Income (UBI), a negative income tax, or a comparable guarantee. By 2035, income security persists across electoral cycles and becomes culturally normalized. Work remains meaningful for status and identity but becomes less central to basic survival for large segments of the population. The politics of mass employability cools, and the pressure to treat higher education primarily as a jobs pipeline weakens.

4.2.2 Higher education impacts

In 2026, Universities remain dominated by the “job ticket” logic. Even where leaders talk about broader purposes, funding, recruitment, and student choice are still anchored in labor-market payoffs. By 2030 institutions reposition more explicitly toward the development of civic culture, research, and high-end capability development. Employability does not disappear, but it becomes less critical to the economics of higher education. Program design shifts toward depth, judgment, and public value rather than volume. In 2035, mass participation contracts as a default pathway into work. Higher education does not become irrelevant but shrinks markedly. Strong institutions thrive as cultural and research assets and as sites of high-end skill and knowledge formation where advanced capability and social capital still matter.

4.2.3 Stakeholder logic

Business moves from degree-based bulk screening toward direct evidence for most roles, while competing intensely for scarce judgment-heavy positions. Students shift from necessity-driven enrollment toward preference-driven participation, with high-agency learners seeking mastery, networks, and intellectual identity while others engage intermittently or opt out. Universities move from mass credential factories toward institutions that justify themselves through verified skills formation, research contribution, and civic value. Meanwhile, society and parents reduce anxieties about “the degree or else” bargain; status competition persists mainly at the top. By 2035, some universities thrive primarily as high skill formation and research institutions in a society where employability is less central to survival. Lower tier institutions may remain relevant as sites for socialization, with education as an optional part of their value proposition. Still, with the weakening of the jobs ladder, the logic of massification evaporates and the higher education sector becomes much smaller.

4.2.4 Key indicators

The fastest moving wall is Proof, because elite scarcity and high-trust roles still require credible verification even when the overall route to jobs becomes less important. Signals by 2030 include a national income floor being enacted and defended, falling average work hours without collapsing living standards, and recruitment messaging shifting from employability to mastery and community. Signals by 2035 include the income floor surviving multiple election cycles, major reductions in “degree required” norms without a social crisis, and stable demand for elite, high-skill formation programs alongside an overall contraction of mass participation in higher education.

4.3 Scenario 2: Building the Common Good: Successful transformation without cost blowout

4.3.1 Key Characteristics

This scenario assumes that generative AI does not merely pressure higher education from the outside but forces an internal reckoning about the purpose of universities. In 2026, the problem is already visible in that seemingly high-quality academic output can be produced easily, which weakens the link between submitted work and underlying competence. However, the system is not yet in open crisis. Employers still value degrees, students still enroll, and institutional legitimacy remains broadly intact. By 2030, the decisive shift is organizational rather than technical. Universities treat generative AI as a catalyst for rebuilding credibility, not as a compliance headache or a tool adoption race. By 2035, a new equilibrium emerges in which universities retain legitimacy because they have become producers and verifiers of capability in an AI-saturated environment. Reform scales beyond pilots and boutique programs, because faculty have become convinced of the need to change and unit costs remain containable.

4.3.2 Higher education impacts

In 2026, institutions experiment unevenly, but a coordinated design logic takes hold by 2030. Assessment is rebuilt around verifiable proof rather than polished output. The practical implication is a shift toward observed performance, structured constraints, and documented process. Examples include supervised applied work, viva-style defenses, iterative drafts with explicit decision trails, audited portfolios, and sampling-based moderation. AI use becomes normal but is integrated into assessment conditions with clear disclosure and enforceable permitted-use rules. The sector moves away from fragile detection strategies and toward redesign that makes substitution harder and capability more visible. By 2035, the core institutional function is clearer. Universities certify not only disciplinary knowledge, but reliable judgment, integrity, and competent use of AI under conditions where error costs matter.

4.3.3 Stakeholder logic

Although many traditional jobs in the information economy disappear, new jobs come to replace them. Employers remain willing to treat degrees as useful hiring filters because proof becomes legible and comparable, reducing the need for costly additional screening. Students accept higher effort because standards are transparent and consistently enforced, and because credible proof continues to translate into opportunity. Low-effort participation declines at the margin, but the average capability of graduates rises. Universities shift incentives internally, moving from throughput and volume toward quality assurance and verification capacity. Funders and households continue to support the sector because it can demonstrate value in terms that survive an AI-era skepticism test. The bottom line is that by 2035, higher education remains broadly viable because it successfully reasserts its core role as a scalable credibility system and does so without pricing itself out of reach.

4.3.4 Key Indicators

The fastest moving wall is Proof, but in this scenario, it is pushed outward through redesign by universities. By 2030, a key indicator would be institution-wide moves toward 'portfolio-plus-defense' models, systematic moderation, clear disclosure norms, and employer uptake of verified proof provided by universities. By 2035, key signs would include stabilized employer trust in degrees, reduced reliance on external testing to validate graduates, and higher education sector norms in which verification and integrity are treated as routine operations rather than exceptional interventions. Overall job numbers for new graduates in the knowledge economy would need to remain steady or grow.

4.4 Scenario 3. Muddling Along: AI slows (or diffusion slows)

4.4.1 Key Characteristics

In 2026, public narratives continue to assume rapid and near-universal disruption from generative AI, yet realized impacts remain uneven. Capability is advancing, but diffusion is constrained by non-technical frictions: the costs of integration, uncertainty over liability, weak data governance, organizational resistance, and the practical difficulty of redesigning workflows at scale. In this scenario, the "AI shock" is postponed. By 2030, either frontier improvement slows for a period or, more plausibly, adoption slows

because governance and economics become binding constraints or some kind of disastrous external event causes adopters to lose confidence in the project (Sample, 2026). AI is adopted but is gradually integrated into existing workflows. Many jobs in the information economy are lost, but new jobs arise to take their place. By 2035, AI is normal infrastructure, but the shift is akin to the transformation produced by the appearance of the internet rather than sudden replacement. Higher education, like society at large, receives a window of time in which to adjust.

4.4.2 Higher education impacts

In 2026, universities respond with partial measures such as policy statements, tool licensing, and incremental “AI literacy” additions, while assessment formats remain structurally vulnerable to output substitution. The slower external shock reduces urgency, which creates the risk that credential credibility can erode quietly. By 2030, however, institutions invest in compliance processes and workflow modernization. Some adopt stronger assessment practices but most treat AI as an add-on rather than a driver of redesign. The sector’s central challenge becomes whether it uses the pause to rebuild proof, or whether it drifts into a low-trust equilibrium in which the value of the degree as evidence of learning diminishes. By 2035, many institutions have used the time to professionalize verification, simplify assessment portfolios, and build defensible proof routines to preserve credibility.

4.4.3 Stakeholder logic

Employers continue broad graduate hiring in 2026 and, by 2030 maintain many degree-based filters because alternatives remain costly. However, scrutiny intensifies in high-risk roles, and demand rises for direct evidence and demonstrated performance. Students normalize generative substitution especially where assessments remain take-home and text heavy. Universities add overhead (licenses, monitoring, guidance), but deep reform depends on governance capacity. Funders and households tolerate the model longer than in faster-disruption scenarios yet become more value-for-money sensitive as costs rise. By 2035, the structure of the higher education system looks like today’s, with prestigious universities perceived as doing a better job but with opportunities for students at other levels as well. The system has not really improved, but if the jobs wall holds up, universities continue to play an important role.

4.4.4 Key indicators

The fastest moving wall is **Cost**, because integration and compliance spending rises even when returns are uneven. Signals by 2030 include slowing wider adoption beyond pilots, constrained AI deployment due to liability and governance issues, stable graduate hiring, and rising institutional overhead without corresponding assessment redesign. Signals by 2035 include sustained cost-per-student pressure, continued incrementalism across the sector, but gradual integration of AI into existing universities and their educational processes.

4.5 Scenario 4. Bifurcation: Two-tier higher education becomes a stable equilibrium

4.5.1 Key Characteristics

This scenario assumes that the most likely system level response to generative AI is not full transformation, but a new stratified system. In 2026, uneven institutional quality already exists, but mass higher education institutions still make broadly similar claims about employability, capability development, and social mobility. Generative AI then tightens the proof problem. When polished assignments, reports, and projects can be produced cheaply, the evidentiary value of conventional coursework declines unless institutions invest in costly verification routines. By 2030, the system begins to sort. A smaller group of institutions and programs becomes visibly better at producing credible proof, typically through observed performance, defensible capstones, and rigorous moderation. A larger group remains exposed, relying on vulnerable assessment formats and compliance language that is not backed by enforcement capacity. By 2035, this divergence stabilizes into a two-tier equilibrium, with a selective high-proof core that retains employer trust and wage premiums, and a mass low-proof fringe that sells access, socialization, and low-cost completion with weaker labor market signaling.

4.5.2 Higher education impacts

In 2026, degrees still dominate, and most institutions respond to AI through guidance and incremental adjustments. By 2030, however, assessment redesign becomes a competitive differentiator. Tier A institutions expand proof-heavy tracks and make verification visible through defenses, portfolio audits, and structured performance tasks. Tier B institutions increasingly reprice and reposition, emphasizing flexibility, convenience, and completion, often with lighter requirements. This does not necessarily reflect low intent but rather the hard costs of proof: verification is labor intensive, and many providers cannot fund it at scale without pricing themselves out of their markets. By 2035, the system is functionally split. One part sells credible proof and selective employability. The other part sells a softer bundle of access, credential acquisition, and civic or personal development, with limited signaling power in competitive labor markets. In this lower-trust tier, unbundling expands as students combine weaker degrees with external proofs and employer-linked pathways that are perceived as more job-relevant and easier to verify. Shorter degree programs expand and mass BA education declines.

4.5.3 Stakeholder logic

Employers treat degrees as noisy signals in 2026, differentiate strongly by institution and program by 2030, and by 2035 treat Tier A credentials as credible while accepting applicants from Tier B institutions through tests, work samples, or probationary hiring (if at all). Students remain enrolled at scale in 2026, but by 2030 high agency learners compete for Tier A pathways while others choose Tier B by default, seek cheaper or shorter alternatives, or exit. Parents increasingly treat admission to Tier A as a major family project. Politics and public opinion become more openly concerned with inequality and the social legitimacy of an overtly two-tier system. By 2035, the system has not collapsed. Rather it has sorted. Credibility concentrates in a small core, while a larger fringe persists with weaker proof and weaker labor market returns. As long as the jobs wall does not collapse, there is still a place for the graduates of weaker universities and shorter programs.

4.5.4 Key Indicators

The fastest moving wall is Proof, especially for mass provision. By 2030, indicators include widening outcome gaps between selective and nonselective routes, employers specifying “top tier” programs or verified outcomes, and growth of proof-heavy pathways alongside cheap completion routes. By 2035, key measures would include tier dependent screening in hiring, stable wage premiums for Tier A, collapsing premiums for Tier B, and consolidation that concentrates trust in a smaller set of providers.

4.6 Scenario 5: Legitimacy Crisis: Society turns on universities

4.6.1 Key Characteristics

This scenario assumes that generative AI accelerates an already existing legitimacy problem and brings it into open political conflict. In 2026, universities still benefit from a residual social contract. They are treated as necessary institutions for opportunity, research, and national competitiveness, even as public trust is uneven and culture war narratives persist. Generative AI then amplifies scrutiny. When it becomes widely believed that degrees no longer reliably certify competence, and when institutional policies appear performative or hypocritical, political attention shifts from cost alone to legitimacy. By 2030, universities become a political target, not only for their price and ideology, but for perceived failure to protect standards and deliver real capability. By 2035, policy intervention becomes structural. Funding, accreditation, and regulatory regimes are redesigned with sharper performance requirements, stronger audit powers, and more direct steering of what universities can claim and how they must prove it.

4.6.2 Higher education impacts

In 2026, many institutions respond to AI with policy statements and permissive guidance, while integrity enforcement remains uneven. In this scenario, those measures are interpreted as weak or self-serving. By 2030, a wave of high-profile integrity scandals or employer backlash triggers political action. Governments introduce tougher conditions for funding, tighter oversight of assessment practices, and more mandatory disclosure about AI use and verification routines as part of mandatory accreditation. Some systems mandate external examinations or standardized proof requirements for degrees. By 2035, higher

education becomes more externally governed and less autonomous. Some institutions adapt by embracing proof-heavy models and transparent standards. Others experience shrinking autonomy, falling enrollment, and forced restructuring.

4.6.3 Stakeholder logic

Employers turn skepticism into action, lobbying for stronger proof requirements and building parallel hiring systems based on their own assessments. This legitimacy tightening accelerates unbundling, since external actors have both the incentive and political cover to build parallel pathways that bypass university-controlled proof. Students and families become more polarized. Some demand stricter standards to protect value, while others resist as they are seen as barriers to completion. Universities defend autonomy and academic freedom but struggle to justify discretion if integrity appears weak. Politicians exploit the issue because it combines cost, culture, and competence in a single narrative. Regulatory bodies gain authority, and public subsidy becomes conditional on visible verification and measurable outcomes. By 2035, the core risk is not technological, rather it is political. Universities lose room to maneuver because they can no longer secure trust due to their failure to adapt to a system of AI enabled output substitution and loss of credential integrity.

4.6.4 Key Indicators

The fastest moving wall is Legitimacy. By 2030, repeated integrity controversies, public inquiries, employer coalitions demanding verification, and funding conditions tied to assessment proof would be key measures of stress. By 2035 expanded external audit powers, mandated proof standards, tighter accreditation, and a clear shift from institutional autonomy toward direct political control would be likely.

4.7 Scenario 6: Apocalypse: Labor market collapse without a strong income floor

4.7.1 Key Characteristics

In 2026, entry level pathways for graduates still exist, but they are visibly under pressure. Firms experiment with generative AI as a force multiplier, and some categories of junior work begin to shrink, especially work that is document heavy, routine, and easy to supervise. The public debate remains unsettled, and crucially there is no durable income floor that could stabilize demand for education if the “degree to job” bargain weakens. By 2030, the key dynamic is not a one-time crash but an accelerating structural shift. Organizations redesign workflows around smaller teams supported by AI systems, reducing the number of roles for recent graduates. The impact compounds across recruitment cycles. Fewer entry points mean fewer opportunities to develop experience, which in turn makes later hiring more selective and reinforces the contraction. By 2035, entry level ladders are largely gone outside a narrow set of elite tracks. Inequality hardens, and the absence of a meaningful income floor turns the employment shock into a broad demand crisis for higher education.

4.7.2 Higher education impacts

In 2026, higher education remains massified because the degree still looks like the least bad option for many students. By 2030, demand begins to collapse as the return on investment fails. When a large share of graduates cannot access stable entry level work the degree loses its core economic selling point. Institutions respond with rapid downsizing, program closures, hiring freezes, and aggressive price competition, but these measures cannot restore demand if the labor market no longer needs graduates at scale. By 2035, the sector becomes much smaller. Elite skills and knowledge-creating institutions and research enclaves persist, along with a small cultural and civic education segment. Many regional and mid-tier institutions disappear or merge, not because teaching quality necessarily worsens, but because the market for mass participation breaks structurally.

4.7.3 Stakeholder logic

Employers reduce junior hiring at the margin in 2026, redesign work around small senior teams plus AI by 2030 and hire few graduates by 2035 except into highly selective pipelines. Students pursue degrees for jobs in 2026, lose confidence in the pathway by 2030, and exit the system in large numbers by 2035. Universities that depend on volume face severe contraction, while only elite and boutique providers retain

stable demand. Society expects higher education to stabilize youth and supply jobs in 2026, faces rising instability by 2030, and treats higher education as politically exposed and potentially illegitimate by 2035. Parents buy the degree as insurance in 2026, see it as a bad bet by 2030, and treat it as an elite-only status purchase only by 2035. By 2035, even 'perfect' proof offered by completely redesigned systems cannot rescue demand if the job ladder collapses. The mass university model breaks.

4.7.4 Key Indicators

The fastest moving wall is Jobs. Signals by 2030 include a sustained fall in entry level graduate hiring, broad compression of the undergraduate wage premium, and programs shrinking toward small elite intakes. Signals by 2035 include structurally lower entry-level hiring across major sectors and sharp contraction of participation outside elite and boutique tiers.

5. Probability Estimates

5.1 The Big Picture

The probability estimates in this section extend to 2040 even though the scenario narratives discussed previously end in 2035. This is deliberate. The scenarios stop at 2035 because that is the outer boundary at which "thick description" about higher education remains defensible at the institutional level. A 2026 to 2035 horizon captures multiple student cohorts, several hiring cycles, and at least two major policy and budgeting cycles, which is sufficient for the four walls to tighten in various ways and for system responses to become observable. Beyond that point, detailed institutional narratives become over-specified, because second-order effects, political realignments, and technology uncertainty increasingly dominate outcomes (Schoemaker, 1995; Schwartz, 1991; Wack, 1985).

By contrast, the 2040 estimates are a tail horizon intended to capture maturation and compounding, not a second narrative horizon. Several mechanisms central to this paper build over time. Entry-level opportunity can tighten slowly and then compound across recruitment cycles, shifting the demand basis for mass higher education. Credential credibility can erode quietly for years as generative systems lower the cost of plausible output, before employer screening behavior and external verification routines visibly reprice trust (Spence, 1973; Power, 1997). Legitimacy dynamics also often move after failures rather than at the first appearance of risk, which makes later intervention more likely even if early signals are ambiguous (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023). For these reasons, 2040 is used to estimate which operating regime is most likely to dominate after these lagged pressures have had time to work through labor markets, institutions, and politics (OECD, 2026).

Methodologically, the probabilities should be read as conditional judgments about the dominant operating regime shaping mass higher education in the United States and UK.⁵ They are not point forecasts, and they do not imply that other regimes disappear. Instead, they indicate which scenario configuration is most likely to exert the strongest pull on enrollment behavior, institutional strategy, employer hiring practices, and political support at each horizon. The 2040 column is therefore intentionally treated as a tail estimate and should be interpreted more coarsely than the nearer-term horizons.

The broad probabilities for higher education outcomes by group scenario are highlighted in Figure 3.

⁵ The scenario probabilities presented in this paper are not statistical forecasts. They are structured estimates based on what we can observe now and informed judgment about how universities and stakeholders tend to behave. The probabilities were set by comparing scenarios against the current evidence summarized in Section 4 of the paper and applying three rules. First, we assume institutions change slowly, so scenarios that require fast, coordinated reform receive low weight. Second, we treat the "tail horizon" (2040) as more exposed to compounding effects, so downside scenarios can rise over time even if they are not dominant in 2030. Third, we force the probabilities for each horizon to sum to 100 percent. Estimates should be read as transparent inputs for disciplined reasoning, not as precise predictions. If the signals in Section 4 move materially, the probabilities may change.

Figure 3: Scenario detailed odds

	2030	2035	2040 (tail)
1. Utopia	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
2. Building the Common Good	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
3. Muddling along	Low	Low	Very Low
4. Bifurcation: The Proof Economy	High	High	Medium
5. Legitimacy Crisis	High	High	High
6. Apocalypse	Medium	Medium	High

Very Low risk
 Low risk
 Medium risk
 High risk

Source. Developed by authors.

5.2 Changes in the Dynamics of Probabilities

Taken together, the probabilities imply a system under simultaneous but uneven strain, driven by the interaction of the four walls and by the fact that adjustment speeds differ sharply. The paper's core claim is not that higher education inevitably collapses, nor that it smoothly reforms. It is that generative AI changes what can be produced cheaply faster than institutions, employers, and regulators can rebuild credible proof, and that this mismatch pushes the system toward mixed equilibria with a long-term trend toward bad outcomes for the current system of mass higher education. Across 2026, 2030, 2035, and the 2040 tail horizon, the wall dynamics reinforce each other as shown in Figure 5. Proof pressure raises costs, cost constraints limit proof restoration, jobs tightening weakens demand tolerance for cost and time, and legitimacy converts accumulated strain into policy and funding constraints. This interaction explains why the distribution places most probability in the mixed zone first, then shifts more weight toward legitimacy-driven disruption by 2035 and thickens risk by 2040.

In 2026, the proof wall is already closing in. Generative AI has made plausible output cheap and widely available, which means a growing share of the work universities have historically treated as evidence of learning has become hard to attribute and defend (Freeman, 2025; Watson & Rainie, 2026). The sector is no longer arguing about whether students are using AI. It is slowly beginning to negotiate what counts as credible evidence under conditions of routine use and contested authorship. Quality assurance guidance and market signals point in the same direction. Detection is not a reliable enforcement technology, and institutions should not assume that attribution can be achieved through detection tools alone (Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education [QAA], 2023; OpenAI, 2023).⁶ Furthermore, generative AI can improve the surface quality of work while weakening its meaning as evidence of individual competence, including by increasing similarity across submissions (Doshi & Hauser, 2024). The result is not just individual cheating at scale, but system-wide signal degradation. When it becomes clear to employers that this is the case, the system's continued credibility will come to depend on whether universities are

⁶ The research literature explains why this is not a niche technical annoyance but a governance issue. Detectors raise fairness and due process risks, including documented bias against non-native English writers, and they are vulnerable to simple evasion routes such as paraphrasing (Liang et al., 2023; Krishna et al., 2023).

willing to redesign assessments such that graduate credentials continue to be seen as acceptable proxies for competence. This is what we call proof pressure.

Proof pressure, however, collides with cost. The necessary reforms are labor intensive. They rely on supervised performance, oral defense, authenticated tasks, structured process evidence, moderation, and the dispute-handling machinery required to adjudicate contested cases fairly (Power, 1997; Archibald & Feldman, 2011; Burns et al., 2026). Verification behaves like audit work. It adds overhead precisely when trust is falling, which is when disputes, grievances, and enforcement costs rise (Power, 1997).⁷ Even if they could agree on what needs to be done, few universities have the surfeit of resources required to incentivize faculty to teach and assess differently. But without incentives it will be difficult to change the mindset of entrenched faculties who in their teaching act more like independent subcontractors than industrial workers.⁸ And the flood of popular press articles questioning whether a BA degree is “still worth it” indicate that most consumers are unlikely to agree to price hikes to fund more labor-intensive verification approaches. Unfortunately for the current system, the legitimacy-bearing parts of the product are the least automatable and the most politically consequential.

The jobs wall interacts with both proof and cost by shaping demand. The college degree premium is still relevant in the United States and remains an important demand stabilizer (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2025).⁹ But mass participation depends less on the average degree premium and more on the perceived availability of entry-level jobs that make the investment feel rational for students and their families.¹⁰ In 2025 and 2026, employer signals are already consistent with tightening at the margin.¹¹ Other evidence strengthens the claim that this is not only a cyclical problem. Employers report AI-driven substitution at junior levels, including “AI before hiring” behavior and reported reductions in entry-level positions (British Standards Institution, 2025). And high-frequency payroll data is consistent with early-career divergence in AI-exposed occupations, with declines for younger workers alongside stable employment for experienced ones (Brynjolfsson et al., 2025). Perceptions amplify these mechanisms because households adjust willingness-to-pay based on expectations, not on lagging labor statistics. Survey and polling evidence show widespread concern about AI’s labor market effects, which can weaken the degree-to-work bargain before aggregates confirm any structural shift (Reuters, 2025; Pew Research Center, 2025; Acas, 2025). The important point is not that labor markets necessarily collapse. It is that entry ladders can narrow, hiring can become more selective, and employer screening can intensify, especially when proof signals become easier to fake.

Legitimacy is the lagging wall, but it converts strain into constraint. In 2026, legitimacy pressure is already visible as polarized confidence and value-for-money skepticism in the US, and as increasingly mainstream

⁷ While it is true that AI can raise staff productivity in drafting, feedback, and support functions, these savings do not cancel out the costs of credible verification at scale and the governance and IT risk requirements that accompany safe deployment (QAA, 2023; EDUCAUSE, 2025).

⁸ If the system were currently over-resourced it might be possible to create incentives for full-scale assessment overhaul, but the 2026 baseline does not show a lot of slack. In the UK, declining resources and reliance on cross-subsidy models are already being framed in university reporting as structural pressures, with many providers forecasting deficits and some facing acute liquidity risk (Bolton & Lewis, 2025; Office for Students, 2025; Ogden & Waltmann, 2024). In the US, the same constraint appears through persistent margin pressure from various sources. Institutions face constrained pricing power, aid competition, and inflation-adjusted revenue challenges, while net tuition often covers a declining share of education-related expenditures (College Board, 2025; State Higher Education Executive Officers Association, 2025).

⁹ Recent reporting indicates that this is less true of Great Britain, making the situation there potential more precarious than in the US. See, for example <https://fortune.com/2025/12/03/university-gen-z-graduates-pay-premium-lower-than-millennials-job-market-struggles-united-kingdom/>

¹⁰ Current immigration policies in the UK and US do not make it likely that an increase in foreign fee-paying students can be counted on to make up for losses of domestic students who are unwilling/unable to pay higher costs for BA education.

¹¹ NACE forecasts broadly flat graduate hiring in the US, while UK employer reporting indicates sharper contraction and extreme competition per vacancy (NACE, 2025; ISE, 2025).

value-for-money politics and regulatory tightening in the UK (Gallup, 2025; Pew Research Center, 2024; YouGov, 2025; Office for Students, 2025). AI intensifies legitimacy risk because the “fake work” story is simple, transmissible, and politically usable. Legitimacy thus becomes a test of transparency, accountability, and demonstrable controls, not an abstract debate about pedagogy (National Institute of Standards and Technology [NIST], 2023; OECD, 2026). If universities cannot explain how learning claims remain defensible under AI conditions, political and regulatory bodies are likely to treat higher education less as a public good and more as a regulated consumer market, particularly for low-trust segments.

6. Conclusion

6.1 A reality check

This paper set out to do something the current debate mostly avoids. It treats generative AI as a structural shock to the evidentiary foundations of mass higher education, then asks what plausible futures follow when the sector’s incentives, budgets, labor markets, and politics are allowed to behave the way they can be expected to behave in real life. That is why we used scenarios, not forecasts. The goal was not to win the argument by declaring either utopia or apocalypse. It was to cut through confident handwaving and show how a small number of binding constraints can generate a complex, mixed reality that is uncomfortable precisely because it is realistic (OECD, 2026).

The paper’s distinctive contribution is the integrated “four walls” account: proof, cost, legitimacy, and jobs. The walls are not metaphors for mood, rather they are interacting constraint systems. Generative AI makes high-quality academic output cheap, but it does not make trust cheap. That asymmetry puts pressure on the proof wall first, because universities cannot credibly treat much student output as evidence of learning when attribution is contested and detection is unreliable (QAA, 2023; OpenAI, 2023; Liang et al., 2023). The cost wall then binds because the only robust substitutes for cheap proof are labor-intensive: supervised performance, oral defense, authenticated tasks, sampled moderation, and the due-process machinery to adjudicate contested cases (Power, 1997; Archibald & Feldman, 2011). Legitimacy questions convert proof and cost strain into enforceable constraints. When households and policymakers perceive weak value, contested standards, and unstable outcomes, consent becomes conditional, polarized, and increasingly interventionist (Gallup, 2025; Pew Research Center, 2024; Office for Students, 2025). The jobs wall, which is mostly outside the control of universities, compounds the effects of the other walls by weakening the degree-to-work bargain, even if aggregate earnings premiums remain. Entry-level ladders can thin out while the macro gradient persists, and early signals already point in that direction (BLS, 2025; NACE, 2025; ISE, 2025; Brynjolfsson et al., 2025).

By 2030, these interactions are likely to produce a sequencing outcome rather than a single shock. The key point to appreciate is that the walls do not move independently. Proof pressure raises cost, cost pressure limits the ability of institutions to provide proof, jobs tightening reduces demand tolerance for cost, and legitimacy pressure rises as these changes become visible. The most plausible outcome, therefore, is a sorting equilibrium in which a subset of institutions pays for proof and preserves credibility with employers, while the majority economize on verification and shift risk outward to employers and students. Employers respond rationally by differentiating more sharply among providers and substituting external screening where credentials are perceived as untrustworthy (British Standards Institute, 2025; QAA, 2023). This is why our probability distribution places the highest near-term weight on bifurcation as the default outcome, while reserving meaningful probability for muddling along. In scenario terms, Bifurcation and Muddling Along are most likely in 2030 because both can emerge without coordinated action by universities or regulators.

By 2035, legitimacy becomes the forcing function because distributional questions cannot be deferred. If proof-intensive assessment becomes a legitimacy requirement, systems must either fund fewer students at higher cost, accept weaker proof for mass participation, or shift verification onto external mechanisms. Each pathway changes the political economy, and policy tends to tighten after visible failures rather than before (OECD, 2026; NIST, 2023). At the same time, jobs effects compound across recruitment cycles. Small annual reductions in junior inflows become a cohort problem by the mid-2030s, and cohort scarring

becomes politically important when private costs remain high and transitions look weaker (Brynjolfsson et al., 2025; Pew Research Center, 2024). This interaction explains why the likeliest outcomes turn negative by 2035 rather than remaining anchored in bifurcation indefinitely. Bifurcation can persist as an equilibrium for a time because it does not require coordination. Legitimacy crisis emerges when tolerance breaks, when weak assurance becomes politically unacceptable, and when intervention narrows institutional autonomy and constrains funding and recruitment.

The 2040 tail matters because the largest effects are compounding and lagged. Recruitment cycles, institutional consolidation, and policy response are slow-moving. This inertia allows problems to accumulate and become visible only after multiple cohorts have experienced weaker transitions and multiple rounds of cost cutting have reduced the credibility-bearing elements of the offer. By 2040, the revised distribution thickens the downside tail not because collapse is treated as the base case, but because the interaction of proof scarcity, constrained financing, thinner entry ladders, and volatile legitimacy consent can convert chronic strain into abrupt contraction.

AI shifts scarcity from production to proof, and the effort required to rebuild proof at scale collides with fiscal fragility, labor market sorting, and political consent. The scenario probabilities reflect that interaction across 2026, 2030, 2035, and 2040, and explain why mixed regimes dominate first, then yield increasing weight to legitimacy-driven disruption and a materially greater risk of mass disruption by 2040.

6.2 Why we could be wrong (but don't think we are)

Readers may well ask why we believe that some scenarios about AI and mass BA level education are low probability, even though versions of them are frequently mentioned in the popular press.

Regarding Utopia, the manifest unwillingness of tech titans to pay even minimal taxes on their income makes us skeptical that they or their companies will willingly fund a scheme of universal basic income that would allow most human beings to benefit from the frequently promised AI paradise of future abundance (Diamandis, 2023). And the actions of governments to force tech leaders and companies to pay their fair share is disheartening. Readers who believe that this might change after AI has eliminated the need for most human labor are free to increase the probability of the utopian outcome.

As for Creating the Common Good, the biggest problems are the speed at which universities would have to react and the extreme difficulty of creating a coordinated response. We speak here of the system of mass higher education, but this is a somewhat misleading term for it implies deep connections across the members of the system that would allow positive reforms at one institution to be quickly adapted by others. In fact, especially in the US, where there is no single regulatory body to force change, each actor in the system is remarkably autonomous. And even within the walls of a single university different actors have different incentives to change. The Creating the Common Good scenario assumes that in a very short time frame, all universities (or at least a large percentage of them) will recognize the problem, agree on a solution (or a set of solutions), and implement these solutions in ways that are not overly expensive. Furthermore, it assumes that jobs will remain available for most graduates despite the institution of AI in the workplace, which seems unlikely to us. To be sure, a near death experience concentrates the mind, but in our view even a brush with collapse is unlikely to concentrate the mind of the current system fast enough to save it. Those who disagree are again free to increase the percentage chance of this outcome.

Muddling along is, in the view of the authors of this paper, the most likely scenario where our predictions could turn out to be wrong (indeed, the authors themselves do not fully agree on how likely this scenario is). Entrenched systems often have higher than expected inertial power, and inertia may allow the current higher education system to survive in something like its current form longer than we expect. Furthermore, there is no guarantee that AI will achieve its promise of completely transforming society. Perhaps AI companies will run out of money before they can deliver the results they promise or energy and/or other natural resource constraints will make it impossible for current versions of AI to deliver transformative results at an acceptable cost. It also possible that the current models simply cannot do what the leading AI companies are promising and that they will plateau, requiring a short or long pause before they can

fully transform the world. Finally, a major AI-caused disaster could cause society to pull back from AI implementation, akin to the way that various disasters or near disasters massively slowed the use of nuclear power. Nevertheless, we should emphasize that even at its current level of development, AI is being used daily by millions of students around the world, in many cases to avoid doing the cognitive work that universities claim their assignments require and their assessments measure.¹² That is, the proof wall has already been breached, and universities already face the unpleasant choice to 1) rethink their curricular approaches and assessment mechanisms and bear the costs of doing so or 2) risk a major legitimacy crisis when it becomes apparent that many graduates are incapable of doing anything other than asking Chat GPT for answers. This makes muddling along a strategy that is unlikely to be successful. Again, readers who disagree with our analysis are free to change the likelihood of this scenario.

6.3 A systems failure for our youth

The picture we paint is complex. Simplistic stories fail because they treat higher education as if it operates in a vacuum. Universities can act, and they should. Institutions can redesign assessments toward authenticated performance, build clearer permitted-use rules, expand oral defenses and supervised work where feasible, invest in moderation as a core operation, and communicate learning claims transparently rather than pretending that old evidentiary assumptions still hold (QAA, 2023; OECD, 2026). But acting alone does not solve the system-wide problem. Proof is costly. Jobs are external. Legitimacy is political. If the labor market is structurally reorganizing early-career ladders and if credible verification becomes a premium input, institutional reforms will be necessary but insufficient. A university cannot single-handedly recreate entry-level job ladders, legislate a new social contract, or absorb the macro distributional consequences of rapid productivity change (BLS, 2025; Brynjolfsson et al., 2025).

The absence of a sustained, public debate about what economic and social futures we want under rapid, unplanned, and unsystematic AI deployment is an epic failure of governance. It is a failure of higher education leadership, of policymakers, and of the wider institutions that claim to be responsible for youth transitions. The core question is not whether AI can produce better text, code, or feedback. It can. The core question is how a society wants to allocate opportunity, risk, and responsibility when output is cheap and proof is scarce. Who pays for verified learning when verification becomes more expensive? What does a credible pathway into adulthood look like when entry-level ladders thin out? What mixture of employer training, apprenticeships, licensing, welfare supports, and public investment is required to keep youth transitions stable and legitimate? The sector cannot answer these questions alone (NIST, 2023; OECD, 2026).

Utopian advocates often reach for escape hatches, most commonly that entrepreneurship will absorb the gap, claiming that AI will create abundant new jobs, or an income floor will decenter employability pressures. Some of these outcomes are possible at the margin, and they may be desirable. But treating them as default assumptions is a category error. They require political choices, fiscal settlements, and institutional redesign at a scale that is not visible in current governance capacity. Conversely, apocalyptic narratives often assume an abrupt collapse. The more plausible risk is slower and more corrosive, with a widening gap between elite, proof-intensive education and mass provision that struggles to maintain credible signaling under cost pressure, followed by delayed legitimacy interventions after visible failures.

If there is one message to take forward, it is that higher education is not merely being challenged to “adopt AI.” It is being challenged to preserve defensible proof and stable pathways for young people in a world where the old evidentiary shortcuts no longer work. That requires institutional action, but it also requires a societal choice about the futures we are building and who bears the costs. Failing to have that

¹² For example, see Wilkins, J. (2025, August 8). *OpenAI usage plummets in the summer, when students aren't cheating on homework*. *Futurism*. <https://futurism.com/openai-use-cheating-homework> and Burman, T. (2025, August 28). *ChatGPT usage skyrockets as kids return to school*. *Newsweek*. <https://www.newsweek.com/chatgpt-use-skyrockets-school-kids-homework-2120753>

debate at scale is not a neutral omission. It is an abdication of responsibility to the very cohorts that higher education exists to serve.

References

1. Acas. (2025). *One in four workers fear losing job to artificial intelligence*. <https://www.acas.org.uk/1-in-4-workers-worry-that-ai-will-lead-to-job-losses>.
2. Acemoglu, D. and Restrepo, P. (2019). Automation and new tasks: How technology displaces and reinstates labor. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 33(2), pp.3-30. DOI: 10.1257/jep.33.2.3
3. Acemoglu, D., & Restrepo, P. (2020). Robots and jobs: Evidence from US labor markets. *Journal of Political Economy*, 128(6), 2188-2244. doi:10.1086/705716
4. Archibald, R.B., and David H. Feldman, D.H. (2011). *Why Does College Cost So Much?* Oxford University Press.
5. Bessen, J. E. (2019). AI and jobs: The role of demand. *NBER Working Paper Series*. <https://www.nber.org/papers/w24235>
6. Bolton, P., & Lewis, J. (2025, June 6). Higher education finances and funding in England (Research Briefing CBP-10037). *House of Commons Library*. <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-10037/CBP-10037.pdf>
7. British Standards Institution. (2025). *Evolving together: AI, automation and building the skilled workforce of the future*. <https://www.bsigroup.com/siteassets/pdf/en/insights-and-media/insights/white-papers/flourishing-in-the-ai-workforce.pdf>
8. Brynjolfsson, E., Chandar, B., & Chen, R. (2025). *Canaries in the coal mine? Six facts about the recent employment effects of artificial intelligence* (Working Paper). Stanford Digital Economy Lab <https://digitaleconomy.stanford.edu/publications/canaries-in-the-coal-mine>
9. Brynjolfsson, E., Li, D. Raymond, L.R. (2023). *Generative AI at Work*, Working Paper 31161. National Bureau of Economic Research. <http://www.nber.org/papers/w31161>. DOI 10.3386/w31161
10. Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2025). *Education pays: Unemployment rates and earnings by educational attainment, 2024 (Table 5.1)*. <https://www.bls.gov/emp/tables/unemployment-earnings-education.htm>
11. Burns, M., Winthrop, R., Luther, N., Venetis, E., & Karim, R. (2026, January). *A new direction for students in an AI world: Prosper, prepare, protect* [Report]. Brookings Institution, Center for Universal Education. <https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/A-New-Direction-for-Students-in-an-AI-World-FULL-REPORT.pdf>
12. Carless, D. (2015). Exploring learning-oriented assessment processes. *Higher Education*, 69(6), 963–976. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-014-9816-z>
13. Christodoulou, D. (2014). *Seven myths about education*. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/>
14. College Board. (2025). *Trends in college pricing and student aid 2025*. College Board. https://research.collegeboard.org/media/pdf/Trends-in-College-Pricing-and-Student-Aid-2025-final_1.pdf
15. Daniel, J. (2015). *Making sense of MOOCs: Musings in a maze of myth, paradox and possibility*. <https://www.tonybates.ca/wp-content/uploads/Making-Sense-of-MOOCs.pdf>
16. Diamandis, P. H. (2023, December 17). Elon & Sam on abundance. *Diamandis.com*. <https://www.diamandis.com/blog/elon-sam-abundance>
17. Doshi, A. R., & Hauser, O. P. (2024). Generative AI enhances individual creativity but reduces the collective diversity of novel content. *Science Advances*, 10(28), eadn5290. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adn5290>
18. Duffy, B., & Hillman, N. (2025). *The UK's higher education system: Public perceptions vs reality*. HEPI / Policy Institute, King's College London <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/policy-institute/assets/higher-education-perceptions-vs-reality.pdf>.
19. EDUCAUSE. (2025). *Top 10 IT issues, 2025: Restoring trust*. EDUCAUSE. <https://www.educause.edu/research-and-publications/research/top-10-it-issues-technologies-and-trends/2025>
20. Eubanks, V. (2018). *Automating inequality*. St. Martin's Press.
21. Fish, S. (2005). *Save the world on your own time*. Oxford University Press.
22. Fore, P. (2025, December 3). Gen Z grads in the U.K. are earning 30% less than millennials did—new data shows the degree payoff is collapsing. *Fortune*. <https://fortune.com/2025/12/03/university-gen-z-graduates-pay-premium-lower-than-millennials-job-market-struggles-united-kingdom/>
23. Floridi, L. (2023). AI as agency without intelligence. *Philosophy & Technology*, 36(1), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-023-00621-y>
24. Freeman, J. (2025). *Student generative AI survey 2025* (HEPI Policy Note 61). Higher Education Policy Institute. <https://www.hepi.ac.uk/>
25. Gallup. (2025, July 8). *U.S. public's trust in higher education rises from recent low*. <https://news.gallup.com/poll/692519/public-trust-higher-rises-recent-low.aspx>

26. Gerlich, M. (2025). AI tools in society: Impacts on cognitive offloading and the future of critical thinking. *Societies*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc15010006>
27. Gill, S. S., Xu, M., Patros, P., Wu, H., et al. (2024). Transformative effects of ChatGPT on modern education: Emerging era of AI chatbots. *Internet of Things and Cyber-Physical Systems*, 4, 19–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iotcps.2023.06.002>
28. Institute of Student Employers. (2025). *Student recruitment survey 2025* [Report]. https://ise.org.uk/userfiles/pages/files/reports/student_recruitment_survey_2025.pdf
29. Ji, Z., Lee, N., Frieske, R., Yu, T., Su, D., Xu, Y., Ishii, E., Bang, Y., Chen, D., Dai, W., Chan, H. S., Madotto, A., & Fung, P. (2023). Survey of hallucination in natural language generation. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(12). doi:10.1145/3571730
30. Kasneci, E., Sessler, K., Krusche, S., et al. (2023). ChatGPT for good? On opportunities and challenges of large language models for education. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 103, 102274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2023.102274>
31. Kosmyna, N., Hauptmann, E. et al. "Your brain on ChatGPT: Accumulation of cognitive debt when using an ai assistant for essay writing task." *arXiv*. arXiv:2506.08872 (2025).
32. Krishna, S., Song, Y., & Pant, A. (2023). Paraphrasing evades detector of AI-generated text, but retrieval is an effective defense. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.13408>
33. Kulik, J. A., & Fletcher, J. D. (2016). Effectiveness of intelligent tutoring systems: A meta-analytic review. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(1), 42–78. doi:10.3102/0034654315581420
Lab. <https://digitaleconomy.stanford.edu/publications/canaries-in-the-coal-mine>
34. Lara, S. (2025, March 3). *Skills-based hiring 2025 report*. LinkedIn Economic Graph Research Institute. <https://economicgraph.linkedin.com/content/dam/me/economicgraph/en-us/PDF/skills-based-hiring-march-2025.pdf>
35. Liang, W., Yuksekgonul, M., Mao, Y., Wu, E., & Zou, J. (2023). GPT detectors are biased against non-native English writers. *Patterns*, 4(7), 100779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2023.100779>
36. Moody, J. (2025, November 25). Moody's projects a negative outlook for higher education. *Inside Higher Ed*. <https://www.insidehighered.com/news/business/financial-health/2025/11/25/moodys-projects-negative-outlook-higher-education>
37. NACE. (2025). *Job Outlook 2026*. National Association of Colleges and Employers. <https://www.naceweb.org/research/reports/job-outlook/2026/>
38. National Institute of Standards and Technology [NIST]. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0)*. <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.AI.100-1>
39. Noy, S., & Zhang, W. (2023). Experimental evidence on the productivity effects of generative artificial intelligence. *Science*, 381(6654), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adh2586>
40. OECD. (2023). *Digital education outlook 2023: Towards an effective digital education ecosystem*. OECD Publishing. doi:10.1787/c74f03de-en
41. OECD. (2026). *OECD Digital Education Outlook 2026*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/062a7394-en>
42. Office for Students. (2025). *Consultation on the future approach to quality regulation*. Office for Students https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/media/ufsk1m23/consultation_on_the_future_approach_to_quality_regulation.pdf
43. Ogden, K., & Waltmann, B. (2024, June). *Higher education finances: How have they fared, and what options will an incoming government have?* (IFS Report R325). The Institute for Fiscal Studies. <https://ifs.org.uk/sites/default/files/2024-06/Higher-education-finances.pdf>
44. OpenAI. (2023, January 31). *New AI classifier for indicating AI-written text*. <https://openai.com/research/new-ai-classifier-for-indicating-ai-written-text>
45. Pew Research Center. (2024, February). *From businesses and banks to colleges and churches: Americans' views of U.S. institutions*. https://www.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/20/2024/02/PP_2024.02.01_institutions_REPORT.pdf
46. Pew Research Center. (2025, February). *U.S. workers are more worried than hopeful about future AI use in the workplace*. https://www.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/20/2025/02/ST_2025.2.25_AI-Workers_REPORT.pdf
47. Power, M. (1997). *The audit society: Rituals of verification*. Oxford University Press.
48. Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA). (2023). *Reconsidering assessment for the ChatGPT era*. <https://www.qaa.ac.uk/docs/qaa/members/reconsidering-assessment-for-the-chat-gpt-era.pdf>
49. Reuters. (2025, December 4). *AI's rise stirs excitement, sparks job worries*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/business/media-telecom/ais-rise-stirs-excitement-sparks-job-worries-2025-12-04/>
50. Reuters. (2025, September 30). *Starmer replaces Blair-era university target with broader skills ambition*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/world/uk/uks-starmer-replaces-blair-era-university-target-with-broader-skills-ambition-2025-09-30/>

51. Sample, I. (2026, February 18). Race for AI is making Hindenburg-style disaster 'a real risk', says leading expert. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2026/feb/17/ai-race-hindenburg-style-disaster-a-real-risk-michael-wooldridge>
52. Schoemaker, P. J. H. (1995). Scenario planning: A tool for strategic thinking. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 36(2), 25–40.
53. Schwartz, P. (1991). *The art of the long view*. Crown Business.
54. Simpson, E (2025), A Research Agenda: Is AI Part of The 'Recruitment Recession'? <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5460596>
55. Spence, M. (1973). Job market signaling. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3), 355–374. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1882010>
56. State Higher Education Executive Officers Association. (2025). *State Higher Education Finance: FY 2024*. https://shef.sheeo.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/SHEEO_SHEF_FY24_Report.pdf
57. UNESCO. (2023). *Guidance for generative AI in education and research*. <https://doi.org/10.54675/EWZM9535>
58. Universities UK. (2025, May 6). *Universities grip financial crisis, but at what cost to the nation?* <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/what-we-do/creating-voice-our-members/media-releases/universities-grip-financial-crisis-what>
59. VanLehn, K. (2011). The relative effectiveness of human tutoring, intelligent tutoring systems, and other tutoring systems. *Educational Psychologist*, 46(4), 197–221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2011.611369>
60. Vygotsky, L.S. (1978) *Mind in Society: Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press
61. Wack, P. (1985). Scenarios: Uncharted waters ahead. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/1985/09/scenarios-uncharted-waters-ahead>
62. Watson, A., & Rainie, L. (2026). *The AI Challenge: Faculty Concerns About Generative AI in Higher Education*. <https://www.aacu.org/research/the-ai-challenge>
63. Williamson, B., & Eynon, R. (2020). Historical threads, missing links, and future directions in AI in education. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 45(3), 223–235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2020.1798995>
64. World Bank. (2018). World Development Report 2018: Learning to Realize Education's Promise. World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/28340>
65. YouGov. (2025, September 18). *Two thirds of students in England and Wales say university is poor value for money*. <https://yougov.co.uk/society/articles/52857-two-thirds-of-students-in-england-and-wales-say-university-is-poor-value-for-money>
66. Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V.I., Bond, M. et al. (2019) Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* 16, 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>